

is seen that the plot of equation (2) produced a straight line passing through the origin for $N_0 = 27.0$ (Fig. 4). The value of N_0 has been selected

Fig. 3. Jones-Dole plot for LiCl in DMF at 35.0°.

Fig. 4. Plot of $\ln \eta_{rel}$ vs $N/(N_0 - N)$ for LiCl in DMF at 35.0°.

by trial and error method, and the value of N_0 and k' are given in Table 2. Further it is seen that the

TABLE 2—VALUES OF N_0 AND k' FOR LITHIUM CHLORIDE IN DMF AT 35.0°

	N_0	k'	k'/N_0^2
LiCl	27.0	563.92	0.77

value of k'/N_0^2 for LiCl in *N,N*-dimethylformamide is 0.7; this value falls in a similar range for LiCl in other amide solvent⁸, *N*-methylpropionamide and *N*-methylformamide.

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Spectral Analysis of some α -Benzylmandelic Acids

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HYDROXY acids are very useful in organic synthesis, due largely to the versatility of the hydroxyl group in undergoing a variety of reactions and hence their synthesis is of considerable interest. Baker and Robinson¹ reported that chalcone epoxide on treatment with alkali yields α -benzylmandelic acid after undergoing an initial elimination reaction entailing epoxide ring opening followed by a benzil-benzilic acid type rearrangement. Bharara *et al.*² reported a similar observation in the case of 2-benzylloxychalcone epoxides. However, a systematic spectral analysis of α -benzylmandelic acids has not been reported in the literature. In this note, we report melting point, microanalytical, ir and nmr spectral data of seven α -benzylmandelic acids, prepared^{1,2} by the action of alcoholic alkali (reflux, 4 h) on the appropriate chalcone epoxides. The latter were prepared^{3,4} from the respective chalcones by treatment with alkaline hydrogen peroxide.

- (1) $X=Y=H$
 (2) $X=p-CH_3; Y=H$
 (3) $X=p-Cl; Y=H$
 (4) $X=o-Cl; Y=H$
 (5) $X=H; Y=p-Cl$
 (6) $X=m-Cl; Y=H$
 (7) $X=p-CH_3; Y=p-Cl$

Reagents: (i) Alcoholic NaOH reflux; H_2O , H^+ .

Some characteristic features of the nmr spectra of the α -benzylmandelic acids are (i) the two methylene protons of the benzyl group are, as expected, non-equivalent and show geminal coupling (J 11-15 Hz), (ii) the protons of the chlorinated aromatic ring in **2e** and **2g** appear as AB doublets instead of the expected AA 'BB' pattern, and

(iii) except in case of **2b** and **2d**, the hydroxyl protons could not be traced.

Compound 2a: M.p. 161-62° (ethanol) (lit¹. 162°) (Found: C, 74.70; H, 5.85. C₁₅H₁₄O₈ requires: C, 74.38; H, 5.79%); ν_{\max} 3 440 (OH) and 1 740 cm⁻¹ (C=O); τ (80 MHz, DMSO-d₆) 2.46-2.85 (10H, m, Ar), 6.64 and 6.79 (1H, d each, *J* 11 Hz, benzylic).

Compound 2b: M.p. 178-79 (ethanol) (Found: C, 74.20; H, 6.24. C₁₅H₁₆O₈ requires: C, 75.0; H, 6.25%); ν_{\max} 3 419 (OH) and 1 724 cm⁻¹ (C=O); τ (80 MHz, DMSO-d₆) 2.35-3.02 (9H, m, Ar), 5.78 (1H, s, OH), 6.70 and 6.86 (1H, d each, *J* 13.5 Hz, benzylic), 7.79 (3H, s, CH₃).

Compound 2c: M.p. 203-05° (ethanol) (Found: C, 64.61; H, 4.62. C₁₅H₁₃O₈Cl requires: C, 65.10; H, 4.70%); ν_{\max} 3 424 (OH) and 1 724 cm⁻¹ (C=O); τ (80 MHz, DMSO-d₆) 2.47-2.81 (9H, m, Ar), 6.64 and 6.77 (1H, d each, *J* 11 Hz, benzylic).

Compound 2d: M.p. 136-38° (ethanol) (Found: C, 65.09; H, 4.71. C₁₅H₁₃O₈Cl requires: C, 65.10; H, 4.70%); ν_{\max} 3 450 (OH) and 1 719 cm⁻¹ (C=O); τ (90 MHz, CDCl₃) 2.3-3.0 (9H, m, Ar), 4.5-5.2 (OH), 6.2 and 6.4 (1H, d each, *J* 15 Hz, benzylic).

Compound 2e: M.p. 194-95° (ethanol) (Found: C, 65.24; H, 4.82. C₁₅H₁₃O₈Cl requires: C, 65.10; H, 4.70%); ν_{\max} 3 414 (OH) and 1 727 cm⁻¹ (C=O); τ (200 MHz, DMSO-d₆) 2.38 and 2.64 (2H, d each, *J* 8.6 Hz, *p*-disubst. Ar), 2.85 (5H, s, Ar), 6.59 and 6.78 (1H, d each, *J* 14.6 Hz, benzylic).

Compound 2f: M.p. 129-30° (ethanol) (Found: C, 64.40; H, 4.62. C₁₅H₁₃O₈Cl requires: C, 65.10; H, 4.70%); ν_{\max} 3 424 (OH) and 1 724 cm⁻¹ (C=O); τ (200 MHz, DMSO-d₆) 2.41-2.91 (9H, m, Ar), 6.57 and 6.82 (1H, d each, *J* 13.5 Hz, benzylic).

Compound 2g: M.p. 175-76° (ethanol) (Found: C, 66.30; H, 5.17. C₁₅H₁₅O₈Cl requires: C, 66.10; H, 5.16%); ν_{\max} 3 412 (OH) and 1 723 cm⁻¹ (C=O); τ (200 MHz, DMSO-d₆) 2.57 and 2.64 (2H, d each, *J* 8.5 Hz, *p*-disubst. Ar), 2.96-3.17 (4H, m, Ar), 6.66 and 6.88 (1H, d each, *J* 13.2 Hz, benzylic) and 7.51 (s, OH), 7.8 (3H, s, CH₃).

All the ir spectra were measured in KBr pellets. TMS was used as internal standard in all nmr measurements.

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Polymer supported Hydroxycoumarin Anion. Convenient Method for *O*-Alkylation of Hydroxycoumarin

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THE reagents supported on insoluble polymers have found wide applications during the last decade in various fields, particularly in organic synthesis¹. In continuation of our work on polymer supported reactions² and in view of the importance of *O*-alkylated hydroxycoumarins as a basic compound in drug industry³, a simple and efficient method is now reported for the *O*-alkylation of hydroxycoumarins. The use of anion-exchange resin for *O*-alkylation of hydroxycoumarins which combine the advantage of solid phase synthesis and anionic activation. Owing to the effectiveness of this system, extraordinarily mild reaction conditions can be employed.

Experimental

Alkyl halide in methanol was reacted with hydroxy coumarin anion bound to the ion-exchange resin. Alkylation was complete within 6 to 10 h at room temperature giving quantitative yields of products in essentially pure form. The results are summarised in Table 1.

Amberlyst A-26 hydroxycoumarin anion: Commercial strongly basic anion-exchange resin in the